

X-Ray K-Absorption Chemical Shifts of some Phenanthroline Copper Complexes

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X-Ray K-absorption studies have been made on two ternary phenanthroline copper(II) complexes using a 0.4 M Cauchois type bent crystal X-ray spectrograph. The chemical shifts for these complexes as well as those of the intermediate compounds, formed during the synthesis of the complexes, have been discussed in the light of the ionic character of the complexes.

As a ligand 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) enjoys a very special place because of its strong π -acceptor property. This becomes even more important when the central metal ion in question is copper(II) which has $3d^9$ -electron configuration. There has been considerable interest in the chemistry of ternary complexes of copper(II) containing a bidentate aromatic nitrogen base such as 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and a bidentate oxygen donor ligand or an amino acid¹⁻⁶, as some of these could possibly serve as models for enzyme-metal ion-substrate complexes. The present communication describes the results of X-ray spectroscopic investigations on the following two copper(II) complexes: (i) Cu(phen) [mal(2-)]. 2H₂O i.e. (1,10-phenanthroline) [malonato(2-)]copper(II) dihydrate, and (ii) {(Cu(phen) [ser(1-)]₂ (SO₄)}₂, i.e. (1,10-phenanthroline)[serinato(1-)]copper(II) sulphate.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the copper K-absorption edges for the two complexes. Table 1 includes various values of X-ray absorption parameters. It also includes the edge-shift and edge-width values of the intermediate compounds^{7,8} for the purpose of comparison.

If we have a perusal of the sequence of synthesis of malonato compound, we find that the compound has been obtained in the following way:

Fig. 1. K-edge and the near edge structure at the K-absorption edge of copper in its copper(II)-phenanthroline complexes: (A) (1,10-phenanthroline)[malonato(2-)]copper(II) dihydrate and (B) (1,10-phenanthroline)[serinato(1-)]copper(II) sulphate.

The initial compound in this synthesis is thus $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2$ is the intermediate compound and $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is the final product. It would be pertinent here to consider the geometries of the three compounds for the purpose of interpretation of observed X-ray absorption parameters. All the three complexes, viz. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have distorted six-coordinate octahedral geometry as shown in Figs. 2(a)–(c). Figs. 2(d) and (e) show structures of the related compounds, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})\text{Cl}_2$ for the purpose of comparison.

1,10-Phenanthroline is a better π -acceptor than 2,2'-bipyridyl; so the back-donation of charge from the metal ion to ligand takes place. It polarises the electron density of the outer orbitals and there is less shielding for the lower orbitals⁹. The more the back-donation of charge from metal ion to ligand, the more effective becomes the nuclear charge of the metal ion. Hence, in the case of a (phen)

complex, the shift of the *K*-absorption edge is larger than in the (bipy) complex.

Edge-shift data (Table 1) indicate that the edge-shift is in the following order : $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Cu}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2 > \text{Cu}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_2 > \text{Cu}(\text{bipy})\text{Cl}_2$. This simply shows that the effective nuclear charge on the copper absorbing ion is maximum for $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and is minimum for $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})\text{Cl}_2$. The sequence of the synthesis of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is given above. The initial compound $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is having chemical shift value of 9.02 eV, which decreases to 8.96 eV in $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2$ due to (phen) ligand. The final product $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibits 14.4 eV as the chemical shift. This means that the entrance of malonato in the coordination sphere increases appreciably the ionic character of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Similar argument holds for $\{\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{ser}(1-)]\}_2(\text{SO}_4)$, the structure of which has been represented in Fig. 2(f).

Fig. 2. Structures of copper(II) complexes. (a) $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, (b) $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2$, (c) $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{mal}(2-)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (d) $\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_2$, (e) $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})\text{Cl}_2$ and (f) $\{\text{Cu}(\text{phen})[\text{ser}(1-)]\}_2(\text{SO}_4)$

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL SHIFT AND EDGE-WIDTH OF K-ABSORPTION EDGE OF COPPER IN ITS COPPER(II)-PHENANTHROLINE COMPLEXES

Sl no.	Compd.	K-edge $\pm .05$ mÅ	E_K -edge eV	E_A eV	Chemical shift ΔE_k eV	Edge-width E_A-E_K eV	Shift of the principal absorption maximum eV
1.	(1,10-Phenanthroline)- [malonato(2-)]- copper(II) dihydrate	1378.42	8994.7	9003.8	14.4	9.1	23.5
2.	(1,10-Phenanthroline)- [serinato(1-)]- copper(II) sulphate	1378.74	8992.6	9003.3	12.3	10.7	23.0
3.	Cu(bipy)Cl ₂	—	—	—	4.62 ^a	16.83 ^a	—
4.	Cu(py) ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	—	6.25	11.81 ^a	—
5.	Cu(phen)Cl ₂	—	—	—	8.96	13.16 ^a	—
6.	CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	—	—	—	9.02	12.49 ^b	—

^a Ref. 7 ^b Ref. 8.

We further find that the relative ionic character is more in Cu(phen)[mal(2-)].2H₂O as compared to {Cu(phen)[ser(1-)]₂(SO₄) which shows a comparatively lower value of chemical shift. In {Cu(phen)-[ser(1-)]₂(SO₄) the copper is attached to one sulphur and five oxygens, whereas in Cu(phen)-[mal(2-)].2H₂O the ligation is through four oxygens and two nitrogens; the change from sulphur to nitrogen brings a basic change in the donor properties of the ligands attached to the central metal ion. Thus the chemical shift value decreases in {Cu(phen)-[ser(1-)]₂SO₄. The values of shift of the principal absorption maximum as reported for the two complexes. i.e [malonato(2-)] and [serinato(1-)] in Table 1, show that the order of these shifts is same as the order of the chemical shifts (for edges) which is expected since the causes for both the shifts are the same.

The edge-widths of the K-absorption edges increase with the increase in covalent character of the bonds if the other factors like molecular symmetry etc. remain the same^{10,11}. Experimental data given in Table 1 show that the edge-width decreases as follows : Cu(bipy)Cl₂ > Cu(phen)Cl₂ > CuCl₂.2H₂O > Cu(py)₂Cl₂ > 1,10-(phen)[serinato(1-)]-copper(II) sulphate > 1,10-(phen)[malonato(2-)]-copper(II) dihydrate. The sequence of edge-widths further corroborates the order of covalency as established by edge-shift data. Cu(py)₂Cl₂,

however, is an exception in this series for edge-widths.

Experimental

Both the complexes were prepared by standard methods¹². The experimental details of the X-ray spectroscopic set-up utilised for the present study remain the same as given in an earlier communication¹³.

References

1. G. A. L. HERUREUX and A. F. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **28**, 481.
2. H. SIGEL and D. B. MCCORMICK, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1970, **3**, 201.
3. P. R. HUBER, R. GRIESSER and H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 945.
4. F. A. WALKER, H. SIGEL and D. B. MCCORMICK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2756.
5. W. L. KWIK and K. P. ANG, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 459.
6. W. L. KWIK, K. P. ANG and G. D. CHEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 303.
7. A. KUMAR, A. N. NIGAM and B. D. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Phys. (C)*, 1980, **13**, 3523.
8. O. P. RAJPUT, A. N. NIGAM and B. D. SHRIVASTAVA, *X-Ray Spectrometry*, 1984, **13**, 156.
9. S. KUMAR, G. N. RAO, O. K. MEHDI and U. AGARAWALA, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil A*, 1974, **29**, 1778.

10. H. L. NIGAM and U. C. SHRIVASTAVA, *Chem. Commun.*, 1971, **14**, 761.
11. A. KUMAR, A. N. NIGAM and U. AGARWALA, *Jap. J. Appl. Phys.*, 1979, **10**, 2299.
12. W. L. KWIK and K. P. ANG, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1982, **21**, 114.
13. B. D. SHRIVASTAVA, S. K. JOSHI and K. B. PANDEYA, *X-Ray Spectrometry*, 1988, **17**, 127.